

Reactions on Solid Supports. Part-3^{1,2}. Hydrogen Isotope Exchange Reactions catalysed by Montmorillonite Clay

K. R. NAGARAJA RAO^{a,b}, ROBERT C. TOWILL^b and ANTHONY H. JACKSON^{a*}

^aSchool of Chemistry & Applied Chemistry, University of Wales College of Cardiff, Cardiff CF1 9TB, Wales, U.K.

^bJones Chromatography Ltd., Tir-y-Berth Industrial Estate, New Road, Hengoed, Mid Glamorgan CF8 8AU, Wales, U.K.

'Deuterated clay' in which the interlamellar water has been replaced by deuterium oxide can be used for exchange of acidic protons in a variety of organic substrates. β -Keto esters and β -diketones undergo rapid exchange of the methylene protons in chloroform solutions in presence of deuterated clay; pyrrole undergoes exchange of all protons, whereas indoles preferentially undergo exchange at the 3-position as expected, although prolonged exposure to the reagent leads to exchange at other positions.

MONTMORILLONITE clay, a member of the smectite class of clay minerals, is widely distributed in soils, sediments and sometimes as mineralogically pure deposits³. Like all the smectic clays, montmorillonite has the classical layered alumina-silicate lattice structure, and contains water molecules in the interlamellar spaces. The effective acidity of these hydrated clays⁴ is such that they can be used to catalyse a number of organic reactions, e.g. esterification, acetal and ketal formation, isomerisation, condensation reactions, Friedel-Crafts type processes etc.⁵. Differential thermogravimetric analysis⁶ shows that most of the water present in the clays can be driven off by heating at temperatures up to 250°; if the clay is heated to higher temperatures little further loss of water occurs until about 700° when the clay structure collapses. The final product cannot be used as a catalyst, nor can its original catalytic activity be regenerated by addition of water.

The acidity of the (hydrated) clay can be increased both by increasing the charge to cation radius ratio, e.g. by addition of polyvalent metal ions and also by decreasing the interlayer water content⁷. This unique property of clay suggested that, if the interlamellar water molecules could be replaced by deuterium oxide (or tritiated water) then a highly reactive source of deuterium (or tritium) ions would be generated, which could be utilised for exchange reactions with suitable organic substrates.

Experimental

Acid-treated and dried montmorillonite clay (K10) was obtained from Sud-Chemie deuterium oxide (99%) and other chemicals were of analytical grade, and solvent were purified and dried employing standard methods. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra (90 Hz) on a Perkin-Elmer R32 instrument using deuteriochloroform as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Ei mass spectra were determined

with a Varian CH5D spectrometer at 70 eV and 50 μ A with source temperatures in the range 200–250°.

Deuterated clay: Clay (25 g) was dried under reduced pressure (1 mm) at 220° for 18 h. The clay was then allowed to cool to 20° in a stream of dry nitrogen before being shaken with deuterium oxide (5 ml), and kept in a tightly stoppered flask until required for use.

Exchange reactions: In a typical experiment 'deuterated clay' (10 g) was suspended in anhydrous ether (50 ml) and stirred whilst a solution of 2-methylindole (200 mg) in ether (5 ml) was added. After 10 min stirring at 20°, the slurry was filtered and the clay washed with dry ether (10 ml). The combined filtrates were evaporated to dryness to afford 3-deuterio-2-methylindole (180 mg). The nmr spectrum of the material showed that the signal due to the 3-proton of the original 2-methylindole at δ 6.15 had almost disappeared, and careful comparisons with the methyl signal at δ 2.75 showed that about 95% of the hydrogen at the 3-position had been replaced by deuterium. The result was confirmed by mass spectral analyses of the molecular ion region under electron impact conditions and comparisons of the M^+ , $(M+1)^+$ and $(M+2)^+$ ions in the deuterated and undeuterated materials. The infrared spectrum of the deuterated 2-methylindole showed additional characteristic C–D stretching frequencies at 2 530 and 2 560 cm^{-1} .

Similar experiments were carried out with the other compounds (Table 1). Dichloromethane and chloroform were also utilised as solvents for the exchange reactions.

Results and Discussion

In our first experiments, we investigated exchange of the active methylene protons of ethyl acetoacetate, ethyl cyanoacetate and diethyl malonate, and found that when solutions of these compounds in chloroform were shaken with the 'deuterated clay' at room temperature 90–95% exchange for deuterium

TABLE 1—CLAY CATALYSED DEUTERIUM EXCHANGE REACTIONS

Substrate	Position of deuterium substitution	Percentage exchange for deuterium (10 min @ 20°)
Diethyl malonate	Methylene group	90
Ethyl acetoacetate	Methylene group	90
Ethyl cyanoacetate	Methylene group	95
Acetylacetone	Methylene group ^a	88
Indole	3-H ^a (and NH) ^b	88
2-Methylindole	3-H ^a (and NH) ^b	95
Pyrrole	2,3,4,5-H (and NH) ^b	88
Indene	Methylene group	15
Fluorene	Methylene group	35
Phenylacetylene	Acetylene-H	90
Ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrrole-2-carboxylate	Pyrrole 4-H (and NH) ^b	95

^aOther protons also undergo slow exchange on prolonged reaction or heating. ^bThe deuterium on nitrogen slowly re-exchanged for hydrogen on exposure to air or more rapidly on shaking a solution in an organic solvent with water.

occurred within 10 min (Table 1) as evidenced by both nmr and mass spectrometric analyses. In the case of acetyl acetone rapid exchange of the methylene protons for deuterium also occurred in presence of the deuterated clay, but on prolonged treatment the methyl protons also slowly exchanged for deuterium. The acidic proton of phenyl acetylene was also exchanged for deuterium under similar conditions.

Encouraged by these successful results we also investigated deuterium exchange of the aromatic protons of a number of reactive aromatic compounds. Pyrrole, for example, underwent exchange at all five positions, although the final product only contained deuterium at positions 2-5, due to re-exchange of the deuterium on nitrogen for hydrogen during work-up. Indole and 2-methylindole rapidly exchanged the 3-proton for deuterium (as well as the NH) in presence of deuterated clay, and on prolonged refluxing of indole solutions with the clay slow exchange at other positions in the nucleus also occurred (as shown by mass spectrometric analyses). Several trisubstituted pyrroles containing a free β -position, also exchanged the proton at this position

for deuterium (Table 1). The less reactive aromatics, indene and fluorene, however, only underwent partial exchange under these conditions, but at the methylene groups rather than the aromatic positions.

The high yields of deuterated products obtained in many of these exchange reactions, and the mild conditions employed, make the deuterated clay a very convenient reagent. Moreover, the clay can simply be filtered off at the end of the reaction and the product recovered by evaporation of the solvent. This makes the whole process highly attractive and superior in many ways to homogenous acid catalysis or to exchange on alumina⁷, especially as equilibrium is achieved so rapidly with the clay. Interestingly, removal of deuterium could also be carried out very rapidly by exchange with normal undeuterated clay. The exchange of protons for tritium should presumably be achieved under similar conditions and one can envisage many other classes of compounds which might undergo exchange under similar conditions. Thus we conclude that montmorillonite clay catalysis should provide a simple, effective and elegant method of carrying out both deuterium and tritium exchange in suitable substrates.

References

1. Part-2. A. H. JACKSON, E. K. PANDEY, K. R. N. RAO and E. ROBERTS, *Tetrahearon Letts.*, 1985, **26**, 798.
2. A brief account of part of this work was presented at the Ion-Exhibition Conference, Wrexham, N. Wales, 1987.
3. R. E. GRIM, "Clay Mineralogy", 2nd. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1968, Chap. 14.
4. K. V. RAMAN and M. M. MORTLAND, *Clays Clay Mineral.*, 1968, **16**, 398; J. T. FRIPIAT, *A. C. S. Symposium Ser.*, 1976, **34**, 261; D. PLER, A. SCHUTZ, G. PANCELET and J. T. FRIPIAT in "Catalysis by Acids and Bases", ed. B. IRNELID, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984, p. 943.
5. cf. P. LASZLO, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1986, **19**, 121; J. M. THOMAS, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1984, **311**, 471.
6. This was carried out on a Stanton HT-M automatic thermogravimetric balance.
7. M. M. MORTLAND, *Trans. 9th Int. Congr. Soil Sci.*, 1968, **1**, 691.
8. G. W. KABALKA, R. M. PAGNI, P. BRIDWELL, E. WALSH and H. M. HASSANEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1981, **46**, 1513.